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SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE INDIVIDUAL SITUATION IN THE STUDENT GROUP

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ANNOTATION

The article examines the socio-psychological factors affecting the state of the individual in the student group. Empirical research data on the establishment of relationships between different levels of the socio-psychological condition of students in a group and the predominant types of relationships between students are presented.

Key word: *individuality, social environment, psychological factors, interpersonal relations.*

Introduction: Currently, social psychology is of great interest in the study of student groups in the system of higher professional education. Researchers emphasize the high relevance of these groups for its participants, especially the importance of interpersonal relationships within the group [1]. Each person who is a subject of interpersonal relations enters as a system of interpersonal relations, orientations, and expectations determined by the joint activities of people and the content of their communication. in various social formations, including small social groups. Relationships in small social groups affect the effectiveness of joint activities, the nature of the communication process and are characterized by selectivity and emotional tones [5].

Analysis of literature on the topic. Research on the psychological study of student group status has been conducted overseas and in the United States. Galina Mikhailovna Andreyeva is a Soviet and Russian social psychologist and sociologist who defines a group as a person whose subjects are united by certain common features, including the nature of joint activities. Artur Alexandrovich Rean is a Russian psychologist and Yakov Lvovich Kolominsky. The data obtained in social psychology do not create a complete picture of determining status differences. The characteristics of students as subjects of communication can be interpreted from the point of view of the social state of development. The student period is characterized by a change in leading activities, a change in social status, and the entry of young people into a new social role. G.M. Andreeva [6] defines a group as a person whose subjects are united by certain common characteristics, including the nature of joint activities.

Research methodology. Problems of groups and joint activities are traditionally considered in social psychology [1]. But many issues, including the problem of the interaction mechanisms of the individual and the group, require further research. One of the important characteristics of interpersonal interaction is the position of a person in a group or status, which means the position of a person in the system of interpersonal relations and the measure of his "psychological acceptability" by group members. It can be considered as a fairly objective indicator of the success of a person's communicative activity. Ya.L. Kolominsky [1] defines status as an integral concept, which includes both objective parameters, for example, a person's position in the intragroup structure, and a subjective reflection of his own position, reflected in different degrees. Thus, in modern social psychology [1,] status is considered as the place of the subject in the system of interpersonal relations, which determines his rights, obligations and certain privileges in the group. It is common to distinguish between business leadership and emotional leadership. The role of the instrumental "business" leader consists of actions aimed at solving the tasks set for each participant and the entire group, and the role of the emotional leader is related to the emotional aspects of the group's relationships.

The problem of individual status in peer groups is understudied in this important stage, such as "student age", which is more studied by researchers of child development, adolescence and young adulthood. The characteristics of students as subjects of communication can be interpreted from the point of view of the social situation of development. The student period is characterized by a change in leading activities, a change in social status, and the entry of young people into a new social role. Adolescence is a special life stage that mediates a person's transition to adulthood. A student who has started an independent life is essentially not independent, he is often economically and psychologically dependent on his parents. Such a gap between the official beginning of social maturity and its actual "non-beginning" is a serious contradiction of this period of development. Student age is a stage for a person when this contradiction is eliminated, active direction and the development of new social functions take place. Staying in the status of a student at a higher educational institution teaches the development of new competencies and new behavioral strategies. contains z. They are often associated with dominant, independent behavior. Students are characterized by a desire to control everything that happens around them in communication, to influence what others do, feel or think about them. They do not want to accept the influence of other people and obey them. characterized by the intensity of interpersonal interaction and the expansion of the social circle. Informal communication that optimizes the emotional state of a person and helps in difficult life situations is especially important for students. The need for recognition, self-respect and self-acceptance is clearly expressed . Reference groups have a huge impact on students. A study by N.D. Tvorogova [4] showed that the level of importance of the group in which they are included is very important for students. The influence of information groups is especially great in relation to the satisfaction of basic needs for students: avoiding failure, maintaining a high position in the group, self-realization and recognition of the individual by other members of the group. avoid conflict between assessments, the need for achievement, high status, group prestige, belonging and acceptance needs. The situation of social development in which students find

themselves is very democratic, where spontaneity and sincerity are encouraged. The university system is more democratic than the school system, and the status of a student is more independent than that of a school student. At the same time, the role of the subject in the system of interpersonal relations has a strong influence on the development of the student's personality. let's turn to the research data of Drozdova E.V. [5], where, among others, the task of establishing relationships between different levels of the socio-psychological condition of students in a group and the dominant types of students' relationships with each other was set. A sociometric procedure was used to determine the level of expression of different socio-psychological conditions of students in the group. The reliability of the obtained results was ensured by using a number of mathematical statistical methods, including the r-Spearman correlation coefficient. The status of "psychotherapeutic" was determined based on the criterion "Which member of your group would you turn to for advice when solving an important life problem?" The degree of expression of each type of socio-psychological condition was determined based on the sum of the accepted choices. Sociometric indices were calculated for each type of socio-psychological condition for each group member. Since the quantitative structure of the groups participating in the study was different, the socio-psychological condition was determined not by the absolute number of elections, but by individual sociometric indicators. Sociometric status indices of group members were calculated separately for all three types of socio-psychological status. Then, in the group of students participating in the study, the average value of the indices for the three types of status was determined, and the general index of the socio-psychological status was determined. According to the research objectives, students with high, medium and low socio-psychological status were identified using the sociometric procedure. identified: emotional, business and "psychotherapeutic". Indicators of the socio-psychological condition of the students in the group by all types and the general index of the socio-psychological condition in the group were interpreted as follows: those who received an index of less than 0.10 are of low status,

those who received an index from 0.10 to 0.20 are average status, indices were classified from 0.30 to higher status. A student in a group.

Conclusion: the analysis of socio-psychological factors affecting the state of the individual in the student group will be useful for the activities of the university's psychological services in the process of developing recommendations for creating favorable conditions for students' adaptation at different stages. training, to optimize the activity of the student group, to optimize the access of the individual to the group, which allows for more effective implementation of educational functions in the profession of vocational education.

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